

Job Satisfaction as a Mediator between Work Motivation, Teamwork, and Employee Performance: A Study at Puskesmas Mokoau, Kendari

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between work motivation, teamwork, and employee performance, with job satisfaction as a mediating variable, at the Regional Public Service Agency Technical Implementation Unit (BLUD UPTD) of Mokoau Public Health Center, Kendari City. The study involved 62 respondents, consisting of State Civil Apparatus (ASN) and Government Employees with Contract Agreements (P3K). Data were collected through an online questionnaire and analyzed using SmartPLS 4.0. The instrument used a 5-point Likert scale to measure agreement levels across four main variables. The results indicate that work motivation has a statistically significant positive effect on job satisfaction but does not have a statistically significant effect on employee performance. Similarly, teamwork has a significant positive impact on job satisfaction but shows no significant direct effect on employee performance. Furthermore, job satisfaction does not significantly influence employee performance and does not mediate the relationship between work motivation and employee performance. These findings offer important theoretical and managerial implications, particularly for improving employee outcomes through enhanced motivation and teamwork within public health institutions.

Keywords: Work Motivation, Teamwork, Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction, Public Health Centre.

Abstrak

Penelitian ini mengkaji hubungan antara motivasi kerja, kerja tim, dan kinerja pegawai, dengan kepuasan kerja sebagai variabel mediasi, pada Unit Pelaksana Teknis Daerah (UPTD) Badan Layanan Umum Daerah (BLUD) Puskesmas Mokoau, Kota Kendari. Sebanyak 62 responden terlibat dalam studi ini, yang terdiri dari Aparatur Sipil Negara (ASN) dan Pegawai Pemerintah dengan Perjanjian Kerja (P3K). Pengumpulan data dilakukan melalui kuesioner daring dan dianalisis menggunakan SmartPLS 4.0. Instrumen penelitian menggunakan skala Likert 5 poin untuk mengukur tingkat persetujuan terhadap empat variabel utama. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa motivasi kerja berpengaruh positif secara signifikan terhadap kepuasan kerja, namun tidak berpengaruh signifikan terhadap kinerja pegawai. Kerja tim juga berpengaruh signifikan terhadap kepuasan kerja, namun tidak menunjukkan pengaruh langsung yang signifikan terhadap kinerja. Selain itu, kepuasan kerja tidak berpengaruh signifikan terhadap kinerja pegawai dan tidak memediasi hubungan antara motivasi kerja dan kinerja. Temuan ini memberikan implikasi teoritis dan manajerial yang penting, khususnya dalam meningkatkan kinerja pegawai melalui penguatan motivasi dan kerja tim di institusi layanan kesehatan publik.

Kata kunci: Motivasi Kerja, Kerja Sama Tim, Kinerja Karyawan, Kepuasan Kerja, Puskesmas.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources are one aspect of management that is always interesting to discuss. In the workplace, human resources are key elements in driving all organizational activities. Human resource management is needed because it will support the achievement of organizational goals. Human resource management (HRM) as the process of recruiting, developing, and retaining employees to ensure an organization function effectively (Robbins & Timothy A. Judge., 2015). It's about creating a work environment where employees can thrive, grow, and contribute meaningfully to the organization's goals. Good employee performance will be created which will ultimately produce good organizational performance through good HRM.

This study was conducted based on the phenomenon that occurred at BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau where it was found that work motivation of employees was still felt to be lacking. Employees at BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau consist of States Civil Apparatus (ASN) and Government Employees with Work Agreements (P3K). In general, there are several main differences between ASN and P3K which will ultimately affect work motivation. From the employee status, ASN has a permanent employee status while P3K is appointed with a contract status that can be extended as needed. If P3K still wants to extend the contract at BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau, it is hoped that their work motivation will increase because they hope that their performance will be assessed well by the leader. Meanwhile, for ASN, their work motivation is mediocre. Another phenomenon that is seen is the existence of problems between management and service units that can be quite complex, including the existence of mismatched goals where management may focus more on efficiency and budget, while service units focus more on the quality of patient services. Lack of communication or ineffective communication regarding important information that is not conveyed clearly by management can trigger misunderstandings and conflicts that can obstruct the implementation of tasks. Different leadership styles between management and service units can reduce the effectiveness of teamwork. Likewise, when the contribution of service units is not recognized or appreciated by management, it can reduce morale and motivation to work together. Uneven distribution of workloads, one of which is related to personel administration which should be carried out by management, but service units solve their own personel problems, can cause fatigue and stress among service unit members, which ultimately reduces the effectiveness of teamwork. Procedures and policies that are too rigid and bureaucratic can also hinder flexibility and innovation in teamwork.

The existence of phenomena related to motivation and teamwork has an impact on dissatisfaction at work, one of which can be seen from the communication aspect that occurs, the tendency for complaints to arise at work, individualism attitudes encourage employees to be dissatisfied with the work environment around them so that it can disrupt synergy between employees. The lack of consistency in previous studies regarding the effect of work motivation, teamwork, job satisfaction, and employee performance is caused by the diversity in measurement indicators, objects studied, methodologies, and theoretical bases used, so this study is important to be carried out to re-test the contradictions in the findings, especially in the public health sector, namely BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center. In addition, this study also refers to research conducted by (Octavia & Budiono, 2021), on the influence of teamwork on employee performance through job satisfaction, with the recommendation to add variables of work motivation, work discipline or work culture in further research. And the researcher added a work motivation variable.

This study adopts a mediation approach to uncover how job satisfaction functions within the relationship between work motivation, teamwork, and employee performance. Unlike many existing models that treat these constructs in isolation, this research focuses on the interplay between

psychological and organizational factors. By targeting a BLUD-based public health institution, the study captures a unique context where structural rigidity meets service delivery expectations. This setting offers a rich ground for testing theoretical assumptions and generating insights that can inform both academic and practical discussions on performance improvement in the public sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Work Motivation

According to Pancasila et al (2020), motivation is the process that drives, directs, and sustains human behaviour toward achieving a goal. Motivation has three interacting elements: need, drive, and incentive. stated motivation is the inner drive that pushes individuals to take action, stay committed, and achieve their goals. Motivation theory essentially discusses why and how people engage in certain work behaviors and this theory has been developed over time. The motivation theory developed by Maslow states that every human being consists of five levels or hierarchies of needs, namely (a) Physiological Needs, (b) Safety Needs, (c) Social Needs, (d) Esteem Needs, and (e) Self-Actualization Needs.

Herzberg, as referenced in Amanda & Ekhsan (2024) developed a two-factor motivation theory. This theoretical framework posits that motivation is a drive that directs oneself to behave in actions to achieve desired goals. Two principal factors exert influence over an individual's work environment, namely the satisfaction factor (also referred to as the motivation factor or intrinsic motivation and the health factor (known as hygiene or extrinsic motivation). According to Herzberg, the motivational factors include: the work itself, the sense of achievement, opportunities for advancement, recognition, and the allocation of responsibility. Conversely, hygiene factors do not enhance employees' motivation to perform effectively; however, they can serve as potential sources of dissatisfaction. The level of a person's motivation by Vroom is determined by three components, namely (a) Expectation, (b) Instrumentalism, (c) Valence, which is the response to outcomes such as positive, neutral or negative feelings. High motivation if the effort produces something that exceeds expectations. Low motivation if the effort produces less than expected.

proposed the theory of the need for achievement, commonly abbreviated as Need for Achievement (N.Ach) which articulates the variability of motivation. Each individual possesses an innate and robust drive to attain success. This inherent drive compels individuals to exert greater effort in pursuit of personal achievement, often superseding the desire for external rewards. Consequently, this motivation fosters enhanced efficiency in individuals' endeavors. Furthermore, McClelland's theory delineates three fundamental human needs: (1) the need for achievement, characterized as a motivational force that incites enthusiasm for work, (2) the need for affiliation, defined as the desire to engage with others, to foster relationships, and to refrain from actions that could harm others, and (3) the need for power, which encapsulates the aspiration to attain authority and exert influence over others. The ultimate goal of this motivation theory is to encourage someone to be able to work and lead an organization.

Clayton Alderfer Theory (ERG Theory) is slightly different from Maslow's theory. Alfeder stated that if higher needs are not or have not been met, then humans will return to the flexible movement of fulfilling needs from time to time and from situation to situation. If Alderfer's theory is examined further, it will appear that (1) the more a particular need is not fulfilled, the greater the desire to satisfy it, (2) the strength of the desire to satisfy "higher" needs increases when lower needs have been satisfied, (3) conversely, the more difficult it is to satisfy higher-level needs, the greater the desire to satisfy more basic needs. Alderfer's view above seems to be more based on the nature of pragmatism by humans. This means that because

they are aware of their limitations, a person can adapt to the objective conditions they face by focusing their attention on things that they can possibly achieve. So that anything can encourage a person to achieve and obtain something according to what they want.

Teamwork

Teamwork constitutes a collective of employees organized under the leadership of a team leader or manager, whose responsibility encompasses the coaching of all members to exhibit peak productivity through the provision of direction, guidance, motivation, and inspiration, thereby ensuring that each delegated task is executed effectively (Riyanto et al., 2021). The fundamental rationale for the necessity of team formation lies in the proposition that collaborative thinking among two or more individuals yields superior outcomes compared to solitary cognitive efforts. Teamwork fosters robust channels of communication. Furthermore, teamwork entails a comprehensive examination of both the procedural and outcome-based aspects of collaborative labor, which encompasses the dynamics of interaction among individuals possessing diverse educational backgrounds, values, and personalities as they collectively fulfill tasks assigned by the organization.

A collaborative work team will generate beneficial synergy through harmonized efforts. Individual contributions yield a performance level that exceeds the collective total of the separate inputs. The extensive implementation of teams engenders the potential for an organization to achieve enhanced output without an equivalent increase in input. The efficacy of a task will subsequently augment productivity when individuals are inclined to collaborate in a team, fostering an environment where individuals are motivated to exert their utmost effort. Consequently, team members must function proficiently to realize the objectives that have been established articulated that there exist five essential strengths in the formation of an effective team, specifically: (1) Team members possess a comprehensive understanding of the team's objectives, which can only be successfully attained through mutual support, fostering a sense of interdependence and belonging in relation to their assigned tasks. (2) Team members enhance the success of the collective by leveraging their talents and expertise towards the team's goals, engaging in transparent communication, articulating ideas, expressing opinions and dissent, and welcoming inquiries related to their roles. (3) Team members endeavor to comprehend one another's perspectives, are encouraged to hone their skills, and apply them within their roles, thereby receiving support from the team. (4) Team members acknowledge that conflict is a normative occurrence and strive to resolve such disputes promptly and constructively. (5) Team members engage in the decision-making process but recognize that their leader must ultimately render the final decision when the team is unable to arrive at a consensus, with the ultimate decision not being a mere compromise (Musinguzi et al., 2018). According to (Quines & Piñero, 2022), in order to function effectively within a team, employees must possess more than merely the technical competencies requisite for their individual roles.

Job Satisfaction

Renyut et al (2017) posited that successful organizations are invariably characterized by the attainment of job satisfaction. Expectancy theory posits that an individual's job satisfaction is evaluated through the lens of goal achievement, accomplishments, realization of targets, and overall welfare. The greater the alignment of expectations with outcomes, the higher the level of satisfaction derived from the work produced. It is indisputable that job satisfaction currently represents a critical aspect to consider in the execution of work activities; every employee is confronted with competitive work environments, necessitating a continual enhancement of job satisfaction development.

According to Da Conceição (2024) and Popoola & Farukuoye,(2017), job satisfaction constitutes an influential emotional response or reaction to various dimensions of an individual's professional environment. Hajiali et al (2022a) articulated that job satisfaction correlates with employees' perceptions regarding their work and its multifaceted components, thereby establishing a close relationship between job satisfaction and the degree to which employees experience contentment or discontentment in their occupational roles. Hajiali et al (2022a) elucidates that job satisfaction is fundamentally a personal construct. Each individual possesses a unique level of satisfaction, which is contingent upon the value system that governs their beliefs and preferences. The higher the evaluation of the work that aligns with an individual's aspirations, the greater the level of satisfaction experienced by that individual regarding their employment. Job satisfaction represents an emotional reaction to diverse facets of a person's occupational responsibilities. In the examination of an individual's job satisfaction, numerous factors necessitate consideration. There exists a range of theoretical frameworks concerning job satisfaction, including: (a) discrepancy theory, (b) equity theory, and (c) two-factor theory.

Employee Performance

According to Ananda & Eriza (2023a), performance is generally thought to be associated with an individual's capacity to fulfill expectations, reach work goals, and accomplish work targets or standards established by the business. Performance refers to an employee's capacity to reach work outcomes in the form of timely, high-quality, and quantity completion of tasks in line with the duties assigned to them. Performance, then, is the result of work implementation accomplished by individuals according to authority and duty in order to accomplish organizational objectives. This performance represents the organization's overarching goal and is determined by the work schedule specified in the employee performance plan. Quines & Nino (2023) define performance as quantifiable action, behaviors, and employee work outcomes. In particular, if employees support company culture, performance can be stated as an approximation of individual employee goals with organizational goals. Through the disclosure of pay increases, promotions, training needs, career development, involvement or participation, and empowerment within organization, performance appraisal seeks to assess, compare, and offer feedback on the effectiveness of the machinery and manage human resource .

Since employee performance affects company performance, each employee must contribute positively through their work (Popoola & Farukuoye, 2017). Performance metrics are observable in both quantity and quality based on organization's criteria. Employee performance criteria are required in order to gauge employee performance. Errors can also happen throughout the performance process, where the evaluation assigns a larger rating than is appropriate. Employee performance data will therefore be legitimate and trustworthy if the performance process is conducted in compliance with the performance assessment procedure (Suifan, 2019).

The Effect of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

Work motivation is a driving force that will exhibit a behavior to attain the objective of self-satisfaction, according to Navajas-Romero et al (2022) In line with Haryanto & Maianto (2024) who also said that motivated people will choose to undertake something since it will fulfill their desires. Human drive, effort, and desire that guides behavior to perform activities or jobs well is known as work motivation. An attitude that demonstrates alignment between expectations and achieved outcomes is known as satisfaction. Every employee is proven to benefit greatly from motivation. Workers who lack the

internal motivation to work hard and strive toward achieving company objectives will perform worse at work.

Work motivation has a favorable and considerable impact on job satisfaction ((Infantri et al., 2024; Zaman & Zulganef, 2023; Adam & Kamase, 2019; Ali et al., 2016; Arifin, 2015). Nonetheless, there is a gap in the research by Hajjali et.al (2022b) and Jusmin et.al (2016) where motivation has a negative and insignificant relationship with job satisfaction. The following hypothesis was created with reference to the above description:

H1: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

Basalamah & As'ad (2021) asserts that motivation and ability variables are the two main components that affect performance. According to Pranata et al (2022), the ability, drive, and support an individual receives determines the performance a business is looking for from them. Employee motivation and performance are closely related, with motivation encouraging people to perform better.

Conversely, studies conducted by Jusmin et al (2016), Jeffrey & Dinata (2017), Tone (2018), Andrea & Rozamuri (2023), Jamilus & Heryanto (2019), Mulyanto (2015), Arifin (2015), and Infantri et al (2024) revealed the opposite outcomes. The following hypothesis was developed in light of the theory and the discrepancy between the research findings:

H2: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

The Effect of Teamwork on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance

According to Munandar et al (2020), teamwork represents the capacity of a collective of individuals to collaborate effectively within a group context, characterized by the existence of an appointed leader and the equitable distribution of importance and expertise among all members within the organization. The proficiency of individuals to synergistically engage in collective efforts to achieve team goals, foster team participation, and realize team satisfaction is also referred to as teamwork. The satisfaction of employees with the results can be influenced by the establishment of common objectives and the principle of equality within a team.

Empirical studies conducted by Octavia & Budiono (2021), Dash et al (2016), Bari et al (2016), Dhurup et al (2016), and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017) have identified a positive and significant correlation between teamwork and job satisfaction. Conversely, this assertion is not corroborated by the findings of Resnadita (2020). From the theoretical framework and research outcomes, the hypothesis formulated is: H3: Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

Hajjali et al (2022a) posited that the establishment of collaborative teams facilitates the enhancement of employee performance through the promotion of team cohesion. Employee performance is characterized by the efficacy in task execution at the individual level, serving as an indicator of the degree of accomplishment in the execution of tasks within the organizational context, thereby acting as a criterion for organizational success. Participation in team-based tasks enables individuals to not only elevate their performance but also to augment their existing knowledge base (Pranata et al., 2022). Empirical investigations conducted by Ananda & Eriza (2023), Phulpoto et al (2023), Octavia & Budiono (2021), Wanyeki et al (2019), Septiani & Gilang (2017), Al Salman & Hassan (2016), Aydintan & Abdulle (2019), Otache (2019), Sanyal & Hisam (2018), and Dash et al (2016) present compelling evidence of a positive and statistically significant relationship between teamwork and employee performance. Conversely,

research by Muhti et al (2017), Auromiqo et al (2019), and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017) identified a negative and statistically significant correlation between teamwork and employee performance. In light of the theoretical framework and the discrepancies found in the research outcomes, the hypothesis formulated is:

H4: Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Job satisfaction experienced and perceived by an employee will significantly influence the outcomes derived from their labor. Moreover, employees who perceive a sense of satisfaction with their work tend to exhibit a consistently positive demeanor and demonstrate elevated levels of creativity. Job satisfaction experienced and perceived by an employee will significantly influence the outcomes derived from their labor (Ilham Sugiri, 2017).

Investigations conducted by Infantri et al., (2024), Aguslan et al (2024), Zaman & Zulganef (2023), Adam & Kamase (2019), Ali et al (2016), Hasriani et al (2021), Dash et al (2016), Renyut et al (2017), Jusmin et al (2016), Arifin (2015), and Djou & Lukiastuti (2020) reveal a positive and significant correlation between job satisfaction and employee performance. Contrarily, differing outcomes have been observed in the research conducted by Andrea & Rozamuri (2023), Mulyanto (2015), and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017). In light of the theoretical framework and the discrepancies in the research findings, the hypothesis formulated is:

H5: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

The Effect of Work Motivation on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction

Expectancy theory states that an employee will be willing to make a greater effort if it is believed that the effort will result in a good performance appraisal and that a good performance appraisal will result in greater rewards from the organization, such as larger bonuses, salary increases, and promotions, all of which allow the person concerned to achieve his goals (Navajas-Romero et al., 2022). The results of research by Infantri et al (2024), Aguslan et al (2024), Adam & Kamase (2019), and Ali et al (2016)), show a positive and significant influence of job satisfaction mediation on work motivation on performance. The research gap was found in the research conducted by Jusmin et al., (2016). From this explanation, the hypothesis developed is:

H6: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with the mediation of job satisfaction at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

The Effect of Teamwork on Employee Performance through Job Satisfaction

Teamwork, according to Basalamah & As'ad (2021), is the comprehension and dedication of team members to collective objectives. Employee happiness can be triggered by good cooperation because it allows for better handling of the current workload (Pranata et al., 2022). Research findings by Phulpoto et al (2023) and Dash et al (2016) indicate a favorable and substantial association between job satisfaction and performance through mediation in teamwork. Research by Octavia & Budiono (2021) and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017) produced the opposite outcomes. The hypothesis formulated in light of the theory and research findings is:

H7: Teamwork has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with the mediation of job satisfaction at BLUD UPTD Mokoau Health Center.

The research framework is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Framework

RESEARCH METHOD

The population of this study consists of 62 employees at BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau, based on the institution’s internal data from 2024. The study applied a total sampling technique, targeting all available respondents. This research followed a quantitative approach with an explanatory design to examine causal relationships among variables. Researchers conducted a cross-sectional survey using an online questionnaire (Google Form) distributed to all participants. The survey included two sections: the first captured demographic details (age, gender, education, and years of service), while the second comprised 44 indicators representing the four key variables. Each item used a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The data collection took place in November 2024.

This study assessed four variables: work motivation (WM), teamwork (TW), job satisfaction (JS), and employee performance (EP). Work motivation was measured using Herzberg's two-factor theory, consisting of 10 indicators. Teamwork used the “Five C” framework (cooperation, coordination, communication, conflict resolution, and consensus) developed by (Musinguzi et al., 2018), totaling 10 indicators. Job satisfaction was measured based on (Quines & Piñero, 2022) with 10 indicators, covering facets like supervision, nature of work, promotion, and communication.

Employee performance was assessed using 10 indicators adapted from Government Regulation No. 30 of 2019 and Ministerial Regulation No. 6/2022, including both Employee Work Targets (SKP) and behavioral aspects.

To test construct validity and reliability, the study employed convergent validity (outer loading ≥ 0.7) and Average Variance Extracted ($AVE \geq 0.5$). Discriminant validity was assessed using the Fornell-Larcker criterion and cross-loading analysis. Internal consistency was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha and Composite Reliability, with threshold values above 0.7. [ditambahkan]

This study applied Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) using SmartPLS 4.0 to evaluate the measurement and structural models. The mediation analysis followed the bootstrapping procedure (5,000 subsamples) to test indirect effects and calculate confidence intervals for mediation paths. Mediation significance was determined by observing the t-statistic (>1.96) and p-values (<0.05) for indirect effects.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Table 1 illustrates that most of the respondents are female, comprising 96.8%, while males account for only 3.2%. According to age, the largest group was 30-40 years old at 43.5%, followed by the 40-50 years old group at 32.3%, with both the >50 years and >20 years old age groups each at 6.5%. In terms of educational attainment, 62.9% of employees held D4/S1 degrees, while 27.4% had D3 credentials, and 9.7% possessed S2 degrees. According to years of service, the category with 10-20 years at 37.1% is the most significant, while those with 0-10 years account for 32.3% and those with more than 20 years represent 30.6%.

The descriptive analysis shows that the mean score for work motivation is 4.11, the average score for teamwork is 4.37, job satisfaction averages at 3.85, and employee performance has a mean score of 4.52. Thus, it can be inferred that the participants' views on the variables fall into the 'good' category. The responsibility item has the highest work motivation score at 4.77, while the lowest is organisational procedures at 3.42. The top teamwork score is coordination at 4.73, whereas the lowest scores are comforting and conflict resolution at 4.16. The average job satisfaction value is highest in communication at 4.23, while the lowest is in work rules at 3.60. For the employee performance variable, loyal has the highest score at 4.73, while quality has the lowest at 4.29.

Table 1. Respondents Characteristics

Respondents	Detail	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	> 20	4	6.5
	30 – 40	27	43.5
	40 – 50	20	32.3
	> 50	11	6.5
	Total	62	100
Gender	Male	2	3.2
	Female	60	96.8
	Total	62	100
Education	D3	17	27.4
	D4/S1	39	62.9
	S2	6	9.7
	Total	62	100
Length of Service (years)	0 - 10	20	32.3
	10 – 20	23	37.1
	> 20	19	30.6
	Total	62	100

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis of Respondents

Variable	Indicator Research variable	Item	Average		
			Item	Dimensions	Mean
Work Motivation	Motivator	Achievement (X1.1.1)	4.63	4.46	4.11
		Responsibility (X1.1.2)	4.77		
		Progress (X1.1.3)	4.55		
		The work itself (X1.1.4)	4.31		
		Award (X1.1.5)	4.05		
	Hygiene	Income (X1.2.1)	3.77	3.76	
		Job security (X1.2.2)	4.02		
		Working conditions (X1.2.3)	3.66		
		Organisational procedures (X1.2.4)	3.42		
		The quality of interpersonal relationships between coworkers (X1.2.5)	3.95		
Teamwork	Cooperating	X2.1	4.55	4.37	4.37
	Coordinating	X2.2	4.73		
	Communicating	X2.3	4.26		
	Comforting	X2.4	4.16		
	Conflict Resolving	X2.5	4.16		
Job Satisfaction	Work Rules	Y1.1	3.60	3.85	3.85
	Promotion	Y1.2	3.69		
	Supervision	Y1.3	3.76		
	Additional Allowances	Y1.4	3.97		
	Communication	Y1.5	4.23		
Employee Performance	SKP	Quantity (Y2.1.1)	4.35	4.32	4.52
		Quality (Y2.1.2)	4.29		
		Time (Y2.1.3)	4.32		
	Work Behaviour	Service-oriented (Y2.2.1)	4.37	4.55	
		Accountable (Y2.2.2)	4.53		
		Competent (Y2.2.3)	4.57		
		Harmonious (Y2.2.4)	4.69		
		Loyal (Y2.2.5)	4.73		
		Adaptive (Y2.2.6)	4.47		
		Collaborative (Y2.2.7)	4.46		

Table 3. Reliability and Validity test

Variables	Item	α	CR	Discriminant Validity				Loadings
				WM	Tw	JS	EP	
Work Motivation (WM)	WM-1	0.807	0.912	0.915	-	-	-	0.907
	WM-2							0.923
Teamwork (TW)	TW-1	0.837	0.886	0.813	0.782	-	-	0.635
	TW-2							0.771
	TW-3							0.826
	TW-4							0.899
	TW-5							0.757
Job Satisfaction (JS)	JS-1	0.886	0.917	0.708	0.705	0.829		0.870
	JS-2						0.839	
	JS-3						0.841	
	JS-4						0.783	
	JS-5						0.810	
Employee Performance (EP)	EP-1	0.830	0.919	0.631	0.610	0.473	0.922	0.895
	EP-2							0.949

Table 4. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Work Motivation	0.838
Teamwork	0.612
Job Satisfaction	0.687
Employee Performance	0.851

Partial Least Square (PLS) Analysis

Reliability and Validity

The technique employed to analyze data is SmartPLS. In this research, there are two fundamental assessments in PLS analysis: Initially, the measurement model (outer model) is assessed to evaluate the validity and reliability of the indicators that gauge the latent variables. Criteria for testing validity and reliability involve discriminant validity, convergent validity, and composite reliability. Secondly, the inner model or structural model is evaluated to analyze the relationships among constructs, significance values, and the R-squared of the research model. In PLS analysis, Bootstrap resampling is utilized to test the inner model.

Indicators are regarded as valid when the outer loading value exceeds 0.7. Nonetheless, an outer loading value ranging from 0.5 to 0.6 remains acceptable. All indicators possess outer loadings that surpass the 0.60 threshold (Table 3). The average variance extracted (AVE) for every construct exceeds 0.5, demonstrating convergent validity (Table 4). Discriminant validity was assessed by comparing the square root of AVE (Fornell Larcker Criterion) for each construct against the correlations among constructs (Table 3), showing that it exceeds AVE (Table 4). The results of the construct consistency analysis, presented in Table 3, are obtained with a composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha value exceeding 0.7.

The highest loading value signifies that the item represents the most powerful or important aspect of the latent variable. The hygiene (extrinsic) motivation is the primary or most significant aspect in demonstrating work motivation, indicated by a value of 0.923. Within the teamwork variable, the soothing aspect of 0.899 is the greatest outer loading estimate value. The findings from assessing job satisfaction indicate that the work regulation aspect is the most significant dimension, rated at 0.870. In the performance variable, the estimated outer loading value for performance behavior is the most significant dimension in indicating performance at 0.947.

Goodness of Fit

The structural model is assessed by examining the predictive relevance model Q² value, which indicates how effectively the observation value generated by the Q² model is founded on the coefficient of determination of all endogenous variables Q², ranging from 0 < Q² < 1, where values closer to 1 signify a better model (Ghozali, 2017). As indicated in Table 5, the R-square figure is 0.551 for JS (R²₁) and 0.427 for EP (R²₂). To calculate the Q-square value, the formula below is utilized (Hair,):

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R^2_1) (1 - R^2_2) = 1 - \{(1 - 0.551) (1 - 0.427)\} \\
 &= 1 - (0.449 \times 0.573) \\
 &= 1 - 0.257 \\
 &= 0.743
 \end{aligned}$$

The predictive relevance value (Q²) is 0.743 or 74.3%, indicating that this research model's accuracy can account for 74.3% of the variability in work motivation, discipline, job satisfaction, and

performance variables. The other 25.7% is accounted for by additional variables not considered in this study, indicating that the constructed model possesses a predictive relevance value or a precise level of prediction.

Hypothesis Test

Hypothesis testing involves examining the estimated significance of the path coefficient and the critical p-value, which should be less than 0.05 to be considered significant. The findings presented are illustrated in Table 5 and Figure 2, specifically: a) Work motivation has a significantly positive impact on job satisfaction, as evidenced by a path coefficient of 0.396 and a p-value <0.05, thus confirming H1. b) Work motivation does not significantly impact employee performance, with a path coefficient of 0.408 and p-value >0.05, resulting in the rejection of H2. c) Teamwork has a significant effect on job satisfaction, indicated by a path coefficient of 0.384, supporting H3. d) Teamwork shows a positive yet insignificant influence on employee performance, with a path coefficient of 0.296 and a p-value >0.05, leading to the rejection of H4. e) Job satisfaction does not significantly affect employee performance, reflected by a path coefficient of -0.025 and a p-value >0.05, resulting in the rejection of H5. f) Job satisfaction does not serve as a mediator in the relationship between work motivation and employee performance, as demonstrated by a path coefficient of -0.010 and p-value >0.05, leading to the rejection of H6. g) Job satisfaction does not mediate the connection between teamwork and employee performance, thereby rejecting H7 as well.

Figure 2. Smart PLS Path Analysis

Table 5. Results of hypothesis testing with R² and adjusted R²

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	t-statistics	p-value	Results	R ²	Adjusted R ²
H1	WM ↗ JS	0.396	3.267	0.001	Accepted	JS = 0.551	JS = 0.536
H2	WM ↘ EP	0.408	1.792	0.074	Rejected	EP = 0.427	EP = 0.397
H3	Tw ↗ JS	0.384	2.991	0.003	Accepted		
H4	Tw ↘ EP	0.296	1.265	0.206	Rejected		
H5	JS ↘ EP	-0.025	0.181	0.857	Rejected		
H6	WM ↘ JS ↗ EP	-0.010	0.164	0.870	Rejected		
H7	Tw ↗ JS ↘ EP	-0.010	0.172	0.863	Rejected		

Notes: WM= Work Motivation, JS= Job Satisfaction, Tw= Teamwork, EP= Employee Performance

The findings of the study indicated that motivation has a significant impact on job satisfaction. The higher the work motivation of an employee, the more job satisfaction will rise, and the opposite is also true. In this situation, when an employee believes their responsibilities align with their personal values, they will experience greater job satisfaction. Factors like responsibility, achievement, and fulfillment enhance job satisfaction. Elements like communication and extra benefits require focus to enhance employee job satisfaction. The findings of this research corroborate the results of (Infantri et al., 2024; Zaman & Zulganef, 2023, Adam & Kamase, 2019; Ali et al., 2016), and (Arifin, 2015), all of which indicated that work motivation positively and significantly impacts job satisfaction.

The second discovery indicates that motivation does not influence employee performance. According to the research findings and perceptions of respondents, intrinsic motivation among employees is insufficient if the workplace environment is unsupportive, including inadequate facilities, insufficient work tools, or uncomfortable working conditions. Moreover, motivation by itself is insufficient if employees lack a clear comprehension of what is required from them. Herzberg's two-factor theory proposes that intrinsic motivation (motivators) boosts performance to elevated levels while extrinsic motivation (hygiene) establishes a solid foundation to avoid dissatisfaction. A lack of hygiene factors, like an unpleasant work atmosphere or poor working conditions, can result in decreased performance even when motivation is high. Insufficient motivator factors, like absence of acknowledgment for completed work or a monotonous routine, can result in subpar performance. Furthermore, not every job has a clear connection between motivation and performance. Regular tasks in the office, whether in service or administrative departments, might not be influenced by strong motivation. Even employees who have been with the company for a long time can face boredom or stagnation (burnout), so despite high motivation, their performance may not improve noticeably. Over a prolonged period, skills, habits, or organizational systems have a greater impact on performance than motivational factors. At over 30 years old, motivation may become more consistent; however, factors like workload, family demands, or elevated job or career expectations can influence performance directly, independent of motivation. For workers aged 40 and above, motivation might not play a crucial role as their performance is largely shaped by their long-term experience and work efficiency. This aligns with (Riyanto et al., 2021), who identified two primary issues in organizational behavior. The first pertains to individuals within the organization, including factors such as biographical traits, cognitive abilities, physical health, personality, perception, decision-making initiative, values, attitudes, work choices, and motivation. The second issue involves the primary challenges of groups within the organization, including group dynamics, group conduct, and leadership. Stress, human resource practices, and workplace culture also affect behavior within the organization. In the behavioral perspective, outcomes or rewards have a greater impact on performance than motivation alone. Performance is frequently influenced by positive (e.g., rewards) or negative (e.g.,

threats of consequences) reinforcement, rather than intrinsic motivation. Therefore, motivation by itself is insufficient to guarantee strong performance.

The third discovery indicates that teamwork greatly influences job satisfaction. Thoughtfully crafted work regulations within an organization promote structure and clarity, fostering teamwork and ensuring a comfortable environment for team members to collaboratively pursue shared objectives. This aligns with Kurt Lewin in (Haryanto & Maianto, 2024), who claimed that a team's interactions are shaped by norms, rules, and group structures. Similarly, Robbins & Timothy A. Judge (2015) noted that the environment is a factor that affects group behavior or dynamics. Successful collaboration will enhance job satisfaction by fostering a supportive, harmonious, and efficient workplace. This study's findings back the research conducted by Octavia & Budiono (2021), Dash et al (2016), Bari et al (2016), Dhurup et al (2016), and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017), demonstrating that improved teamwork enhances job satisfaction.

The fourth finding indicates that collaboration does not influence employee performance. It can be analyzed through the components of organizational behavior, specifically people, structure, and environment. In this scenario, collaboration includes people, teams, and the organizational setting. An absence of acknowledgment for teamwork and an organizational culture that emphasizes individual recognition over team collaboration can diminish the impact of cooperation on performance. Evaluation of employee performance focuses on personal outcomes, rather than team efforts, which obscures the connection between teamwork and overall performance. Additional elements like technology can impact performance more significantly than teamwork; for instance, a well-functioning team without access to essential technology may still fall short of optimal performance. This can be observed in the lack of computers or laptops required for accessing services in the office, as well as the sufficiency of the network provided in the office. These results are consistent with earlier studies conducted by Muhti et al (2017), Auromiqo et al (2019), and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017).

The fifth finding indicates that job satisfaction does not affect employee performance, implying that enhancing job satisfaction does not lead to better employee performance. As per , job satisfaction is a reaction that influences or an emotional reaction to different facets of an individual's job. Job satisfaction reflects an individual's viewpoint, which can be either favorable or unfavorable, regarding their employment. Employment satisfaction is frequently associated with comfort. In certain job types, performance is more affected by factors like skills, experience, or work pressure than by job satisfaction. This is evident in jobs within the service sector. Employee performance may also be impacted by external elements like organizational policies and the resources at hand, including facilities and infrastructure. Job satisfaction is personal and frequently shaped by personal expectations; thus, it may not accurately indicate the degree of performance that is expected. Every person reacts to job satisfaction in a unique way. Workers who possess a strong work ethic can still excel even when unhappy, suggesting that job satisfaction appears unimportant. Excessively high job satisfaction might lead employees to become overly comfortable, causing them to lose their motivation to enhance their performance. This differs from the studies by Infantri et al (2024), Aguslan et al (2024), and Zaman & Zulganef (2023). The finding that job satisfaction does not significantly affect employee performance contradicts most existing studies. This anomaly deserves closer attention. Several contextual factors may contribute to this result. First, the organizational culture at BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau emphasizes procedural compliance over individual initiative. Employees tend to focus on fulfilling routine tasks, which limits the role of satisfaction in driving higher performance. Second, the appraisal system still uses a standardized evaluation format that rarely reflects individual contributions or team dynamics. This reduces employees' motivation to exceed performance expectations, regardless of their job satisfaction. Third, workload distribution

remains unequal. Some employees face task overload, while others handle minimal responsibilities. These conditions may cause satisfied employees to stay compliant rather than productive.

The unique organizational context of BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau helps explain this situation. As a local public health center operating under the BLUD system, it combines government bureaucracy with service-oriented targets. The structure restricts flexibility in promotion, reward mechanisms, and performance incentives. Employees, both ASN and P3K, work within rigid operational frameworks, which dampens the impact of internal satisfaction on external output. Without strong performance-based incentives or organizational innovation, satisfaction alone cannot shift performance outcomes meaningfully.

The sixth finding indicates that job satisfaction does not serve as a mediator in the connection between work motivation and employee performance. Motivation and performance are frequently affected by numerous intricate factors, thus the function of job satisfaction as a mediator can differ based on the organization's context and attributes. In high-velocity roles, like public services, performance frequently relies on targets or work regulations instead of employee satisfaction. When organizational goals and employee performance expectations are ambiguous, even if workers are content with their roles, they may lack the motivation needed to enhance their performance. Job satisfaction may be present, but without specific objectives, it won't greatly enhance performance. Herzberg emphasized job satisfaction as a link between motivation and performance. This indicates that intrinsic motivation driven by motivator factors usually influences performance indirectly by enhancing job satisfaction. Nonetheless, in practice, not all employees react similarly to motivator or hygiene factors. The interplay between motivation, job satisfaction, and performance can be intricate, incorporating additional factors like organizational commitment, workplace culture, or the work environment. Employees with extended tenures might prioritize stability and acknowledgment over job satisfaction when it comes to impacting their performance. The findings of this study align with the research conducted by (Jusmin et al., 2016).

The seventh finding indicates that job satisfaction also does not significantly influence the connection between teamwork and employee performance. Numerous elements can obstruct the function of mediation in affecting team cooperation on employee performance, such as disagreements among team members and insufficient individual acknowledgment, leading to feelings of undervaluation among them. Job satisfaction is frequently affected by several elements, including compensation/perks, workplace setting, and interactions with management. If these elements are not favorable, job satisfaction might stay low despite effective teamwork. Furthermore, in government organizations, employee performance is evaluated based on personal work goals that do not directly connect to teamwork. This research backs the findings of Octavia & Budiono (2021) and Hatta & Said Musnadi (2017), in contrast to the studies by Phulpoto et al (2023) and Dash et al (2016).

This study contributes to the literature by challenging the assumption that job satisfaction consistently drives performance. Previous models often position satisfaction as a direct determinant of performance across organizational contexts. The results from BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau reveal that this relationship weakens under bureaucratic structures with limited performance-based incentives. This finding suggests the need to reevaluate how job satisfaction functions in public sector environments, especially within hybrid systems like BLUDs that combine bureaucratic and service elements.

This research strengthens the theoretical understanding of teamwork and motivation by confirming their influence on satisfaction, while highlighting their limited direct impact on performance. These results extend existing theories by demonstrating that employee satisfaction may operate as a psychological buffer rather than a performance driver in rigid institutional contexts. Future studies should

consider integrating institutional theory or public administration frameworks to enrich behavioral models in similar environments.

This study provides valuable insights, yet it faces several limitations. The research focused on a single public health institution with a relatively small sample of 62 respondents, which restricts generalizability. The exclusive use of self-reported questionnaires may also introduce response bias, especially in a bureaucratic environment where employees may hesitate to express dissatisfaction openly. The study did not include moderating variables such as leadership style, organizational culture, or reward systems, which may influence the strength of relationships among the variables.

Future research should broaden the institutional scope by including multiple BLUD health centers across different regions to enhance external validity. Scholars should consider applying longitudinal designs to capture changes in satisfaction and performance over time. Further exploration into moderating factors such as leadership quality, institutional innovation, and digitalization levels may provide deeper insights into the dynamics between motivation, teamwork, satisfaction, and performance in the public sector. Combining qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups can also enrich understanding by uncovering contextual nuances not captured through quantitative analysis.

CONCLUSION

This study was conducted at BLUD UPTD Puskesmas Mokoau, a public health service institution in Kendari City, Southeast Sulawesi, which has never been the object of similar research before. The focus on the public health sector in Indonesia, especially in the eastern region, provides a new perspective as most previous similar studies have been conducted in the private sector or large urban areas. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to policy development and managerial practices in the health sector. This study examines job satisfaction as a mediating variable, in the relationship between work motivation, teamwork, and employee performance. Although several studies have tested the mediation of job satisfaction, the combination of work motivation, teamwork, and employee performance variables in the context of the public health sector has not been widely explored, especially using the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach.

There are contradictory findings with theory and previous research, which showed that work motivation has no significant effect on employee performance, teamwork has no significant effect on employee performance, and job satisfaction doesn't impact employee performance. Job satisfaction also doesn't affect the relationship between work motivation and employee performance, and doesn't affect the relationship between teamwork and employee performance, contrast from previous studies. These findings provide new insights that contextual factors (such as the public sector work environment) might reduce the role of motivation and job satisfaction in improving performance. This study involves two groups of employees (ASN and P3K) with different employment status (permanent vs. contract). Analyzing differences in motivation and job satisfaction between these two groups adds to the complexity of the findings, especially in the context of staffing policies in Indonesia's still developing public sector. But this study doesn't compare these two groups to gain more insight in motivation, teamwork, job satisfaction, and performance, and it became the limitation of this study. This study provides policy recommendations that are focused on the health center context, such as improving infrastructure, developing a non-material reward system, and improving internal communication. This is different from general research that tends to suggest generic solutions.

This research highlights the complex role of job satisfaction in mediating motivation and teamwork toward performance. The findings emphasize that context matters. Public organizations, especially those operating under hybrid systems like BLUD, require more than internal satisfaction to enhance output. This study offers a valuable reference point for future research seeking to refine behavioral models in public sector environments. Scholars and practitioners should explore alternative drivers—such as institutional design, leadership style, or reward structures—to complement internal factors and produce meaningful performance gains.

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